

Recommended citation: Baier, A., Neef, M., & Mai, V. (2020). Sustainability, Responsibility and Ethics for Engineers - an Interactive and Transferable Course System. In van der Veen, J., van Hattum-Janssen, N., Järvinen, H.-M., de Laet, T., & ten Dam, I. (Eds.), *Engaging Engineering Education. SEFI 48th Annual Conference* (pp. 1398-1400). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Enschede, The Netherlands. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14654360.

SUSTAINABILITY, RESPONSIBILITY AND ETHICS FOR ENGINEERS - AN INTERACTIVE AND TRANSFERABLE COURSE SYSTEM

André Baier¹

Technische Universität
Berlin, Germany

Matthias Neef

Hochschule
Düsseldorf, Germany

Vanessa Mai

Technische Hochschule
Köln, Germany

The Blue Engineering course design promotes socially and ecologically responsible engineering through a variety of alternative teaching methods. Engineering students acquire the competence to unveil the complex interdependency of their social, political, ecological and economic surroundings. This includes the consideration of different values, interests and needs within a global perspective as well as within one class(room). The course design encourages democratic decision-making not only to solve but also to define problems within the course itself and moreover outside of the classroom. The course design is successfully implemented at seven universities in Germany reaching over 300 students each semester. This underlines the high adaptability and transferability of the course design. Thus, participants of the workshop will experience first hand a course design that may be easily adapted to any engineering study program. To underline the student-driven approach of the course design, the proposed 40-minute workshop will be conducted entirely by student tutors. As a backup, senior faculty will also attend the workshop which consists of three parts: 1) teaching/learning in practice, 2) implementation of the course design at different universities, 3) adaptation and transferability of the course design to other universities.

WORKSHOP PROGRAM

- 1) 10 Minutes - The workshop participants will engage in a set of interactive teaching/learning units in order to gain an immediate methodological and content-related impression of the course concept
- 2) 10 - Minutes - The implementation as well as the transferability of the course concept will be demonstrated using the examples of TU Berlin, University of Applied Science Düsseldorf and Technical University of Applied Science Köln. This includes the presentation of the experiences based on a the digital implementation of the course during the Corona pandemic.
- 3) 20 - Minutes - The final discussion will focus on the conditions for successful adaptation and transfer to other universities and disciplines. The discussion will be

¹ Corresponding author
André Baier
Andre.Baier@tu-berlin.de

sparked as a short role play in small groups where the participants take up the different roles at a university in order to identify drivers, barriers etc.

LEARNING OUTCOMES OF THE BLUE ENGINEERING COURSE

The description of the learning outcomes of the course follows a design down process, which means that the learning outcomes on the higher educational levels function as guidance to derive the learning outcomes on the lower levels. For this, the 12 broadly recognized sub-competences of Gestaltungskompetenz of an education for sustainable development have been reformulated as learning outcomes. Next, they were adapted as specific learning outcomes for the course. These learning outcomes are already specific enough to constructively align with the broad range of learning activities of the course as well as with the formative assessment of the students. Furthermore, this precisioning allows for a comprehensive evaluation of the whole course.

DESIGN OF THE COURSE ON SUSTAINABILITY, RESPONSIBILITY AND ETHICS FOR ENGINEERS

The course is a student-initiated course design that addresses the social and ecological responsibility of engineering. Its student-driven character is achieved through a set of over 150 well-documented teaching/learning units which are freely available online. The course consists of three parts so that the students gradually acquire the competences to co-conduct and co-develop the course: 1) Students get to know high quality teaching/learning units conducted by a lecturer/student tutors; 2) Students conduct existing teaching/learning units; 3) Students develop new teaching/learning units and conduct them as wells document them for future use.

TEACHING/LEARNING UNITS OF THE COURSE

Key element of this student-driven design is a set of 15 to 90 minute long teaching/learning units. Each unit must provide an appropriate set of methods to enable any generally interested group with a maximum of 25 persons to acquire a certain insight into the ecological and social dimensions of technology. In order to reach this goal, these teaching/learning units are self-contained units that cover one specific topic and that provide different methods that engage the participants in co-conducting a lesson more or less by themselves. Therefore, the person conducting the teaching/learning units does not function as an expert that simply conveys knowledge but as a facilitator that organizes a complex group process.

The over 100 teaching/learning units cover a broad range of topics within the field of social and ecological engineering. Some of these teaching/learning units help to thoroughly analyze single technologies, e.g. fracking, preimplantation diagnostics, while others address the general effects of technology on society or nature. There are a number of units which address the individual sphere, e.g. mobility and consumption while other units address the global sphere, e.g. agricultural industry, capitalism, climate change. Several units particularly address the work-life of engineers and the concept of work in general.

Along with the wide variety of topics, every single teaching/learning units uses a specific set of teaching formats such as case studies, storytelling and station learning. Most teaching/learning units, however, rely on a specific adaptation and new combination of known methods, e.g. learning cascades, court trials and educational games. Thus they make extensive use of methods that take the shift

from teaching to learning seriously, e.g. role play, station learning, crime scene investigations and educational games.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE COURSE AT SEVEN UNIVERSITIES

The Blue Engineering course is currently conducted each semester at seven universities in Germany. Here, student tutors are in charge of running the entire course as they are only coached and supervised by faculty members. In total, over 300 students attend the courses each semester and over 1500 student have successfully passed the course over the past semesters.

The different implementations show that the course design is highly adaptable to different settings. Typically, the course is a compulsory elective in a number of study programs within the engineering faculty, e.g. mechanical engineering and industrial engineering. In addition, an initiative has been taken up at one university to also include non-engineering study programs such as economics and informatics. Overall, this setup ensures a learning experience that crosses disciplinary borders allowing an interdisciplinary approach to learning/teaching.